

QUALITY OF WORKLIFE OF AGRICULTURAL WOMEN IN VILLUPURAM DISTRICT

S. Lakshmi priya¹ Ph.D. Research scholar, PG and Research Department of Commerce, Arignar Anna Government Arts College, Villupuram - 605 602.	Dr. C. Selvarani² Associate Professor, PG and Research Department of Commerce, Arignar Anna Government Arts College, Villupuram - 605 602.
---	--

ABSTRACT

Quality of work life for agricultural women is the level of motivation, satisfaction, and commitment they experience while working in the agricultural sector. It also refers to how well they can support themselves while working in agriculture. The research attempts to identify the quality of work life of agricultural women. The data has been collected from 150 agricultural women in Villupuram district. The research concluded that the self-leadership competencies significantly influence quality of work life. It is found that the self-leadership competencies significantly influence life satisfaction. There is mediating effect of quality of work life between self-leadership competencies and life satisfaction. To increase their confidence and improve long-term productivity, agricultural women could gain from specialized training programs focused on stress management, work-life balance, workplace safety, and health and wellbeing.

KEYWORDS: *Self-Leadership Competencies, Quality of Work, Life Satisfaction and Long-Term Productivity.*

INTRODUCTION

Farmers' lifestyles are characterized by autonomy, tradition, continuity, and proximity to nature, according to Nitsch (1987). Nevertheless, despite the picturesque way of life that comes with farming, the number of farms is changing the farming landscape. Today's farmers must be able to oversee sizable workforces, negotiate the intricate production and distribution market, and cope with ongoing pressure to develop and adopt new technologies (Ulvenblad &

Bjorklund, 2018). Leadership literature defines leadership as the capacity to communicate a vision and set goals that others share, thereby boosting output, effectiveness, and influence (Hughes, 2007).

The quality of life for farmers has suffered greatly because of the increased pressure and responsibility in the agricultural sector. A correlation between farmers' quality of life and their quality of work is linked to their work environment characteristics (Clark, 2010). According to Kong, et al. (2019), farmers' motivation to work may also be significantly influenced by their ability to optimize organizational management and enhance interpersonal relationships that affect their quality of life. Hughes (2007) highlighted that within an organization, leadership takes on various roles and responsibilities. The terms management, administration, and leadership are frequently used interchangeably in the literature. Though, the three frequently work in tandem.

The literature claims that while management ensures that the organization has enough human and physical resources to meet its objectives, leadership is linked to strategic decision-making. Effective daily operations are ensured by administration. Moreover, administration encompasses the duties required to maintain an organization's smooth operation, including personnel matters, financial records, and the working environment (Fullan, 2001; Nanus, 1992). According to Hughes (2007), organizational leaders should be able to focus on their leadership responsibilities and separate themselves from the day-to-day managerial and administrative tasks.

There aren't many studies that address the connections between farmers' life satisfaction, self-leadership skills, and quality of life. Therefore, this study examines how agricultural women view their work-life balance and examines how it relates to their self-leadership skills and level of life satisfaction.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Joy & John (2023) A person's profession, occupation, trade, or vocation is referred to as their career. It refers to one's line of work, such as being a teacher, doctor, lawyer, etc. There are many factors that affect life satisfaction, but the two most important ones are job and relationship satisfaction (Judge and Watanabe, 1994). A person's perception of how fulfilling their life is greatly influenced by the overall interrelated satisfaction between the two. Since most workers spend many of their waking hours at work, their sense of success, belongingness, and room for advancement are crucial components of their overall self-perception.

Windon and Robotham (2021) found that 43 % of the variance in overall farmers' quality of life was explained by farmers' self-leadership and ability to lead others' competencies. Extension practitioners should develop a leadership program for farmers that will address the following areas: farmers' work-life balance during busy season and difficult.

According to Bogue and Phelan (2005), farms are complicated. Quality of life, according to Molnar (1985), is a global construct that depends on a person's expectations and life experiences (Windon, et al. 2016). According to Coughenour and Swanson (1988), contentment with farm labor affects contentment with farm life. Because farm families measure quality of life on multiple levels, it can be difficult for researchers to interpret farm family quality of life data. Quality of life studies are usually exploratory due to the constantly changing life, work conditions, and current life experience of farmers (Windon, et al. 2016).

For the company to benefit from increased retention and productivity ratios, Kashyap, et al. (2016) comprehended and clarified the idea of employee wellbeing and its connection to their job satisfaction and work-life balance. While examining the information acquired from secondary sources and discussing their points of view, the authors conducted descriptive research. The main conclusions emphasize that workers are a company's most valuable

resource and that companies that support their workers in achieving a better work-life balance have happier workers.

According to Kleih and Kubler (2014), a person's quality of life is positively impacted by their communication skills. Although the latter relationship needs to be confirmed, they suggest that a person's quality of life may benefit further from a sense of autonomy combined with the satisfaction of their need for competence.

According to Lee, et al. (2011), social support, relationship fulfillment, self-esteem, community commitment, psychological and physical wellbeing, and quality of life have all been found to be enhanced by family contact and social group participation.

According to Hughes (2007), effective leadership in a variety of contexts is influenced by several crucial elements. These elements include ethical conduct, strategic thinking, and effective communication. The authors pointed out that effective leaders must be able to receive and convey information in a clear, succinct, and efficient manner as well as offer constructive criticism, making their communication abilities crucial.

According to Fullan (2001), the leadership demonstrated by others can occasionally be used to assess the caliber of leadership. In addition to mediating, starting organizational actions, and ensuring group functionality, a true leader should be able to step back from his leadership role and delegate, assist a group in achieving its goals, and help others satisfy their needs (Gibson, et al. 2002). The group's values, motivations, and goals are personified and represented by the leader.

H1: Self-leadership competencies significantly influence quality of work life.

H2: Self-leadership competencies significantly influence life satisfaction.

H3: Quality of work life significantly influences life satisfaction.

FRAMEWORK

Figure 1: Conceptual framework

OBJECTIVES

- To discover the influence of self-leadership competencies on quality of work life among agricultural women.
- To discover the influence of self-leadership competencies on life satisfaction among agricultural women.
- To find out the influence of quality of work life on life satisfaction among agricultural women.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The researcher uses a descriptive research design to investigate how quality of work life as a mediator in the agricultural women and how farmers' self-leadership competencies affect their life satisfaction. A standardized and structured questionnaire is used to gather information from agricultural women in Villupuram district. The relationship between self-leadership competencies, quality of work life, and life satisfaction is investigated using this descriptive research design.

QUESTIONNAIRE DESIGN

Table 1: Questionnaire Construction

S.No.	Variable	Items	Author
I	Demographic Profile	8	---
II	Self-Leadership Competencies	8	Windon and Robotham (2021)
III	Quality of Work Life	8	Hosseini & Jorjatki (2010)
IV	Life Satisfaction	4	Diener, et al. (1985)

A carefully crafted questionnaire is used to gather information from agricultural women in Villupuram district. This study's questionnaire is broken up into four sections. Agricultural women demographics are gathered in the first section of the questionnaire, followed by self-leadership competencies in the second, quality of life in the third, and life satisfaction in the fourth. All four sections aside from the first are made up of multiple-choice questions. The other three are set up as a measuring scaling technique, while the first is set up as a category.

RELIABILITY

Table 2: Reliability of the Research Tool

S.No.	Variable	Items	Cronbach's Alpha
I	Self-leadership Competencies	8	0.90
II	Quality of Work Life	8	0.86
III	Life Satisfaction	4	0.82

To ensure the reliability of the study questionnaire's results, a pilot study was conducted. 150 agricultural women in Villupuram district participated in the questionnaire verification process. The questionnaire has been modified considering the opinions of the agricultural women. The reliability of the study variables is tested using Cronbach's alpha tool. This questionnaire's reliability is demonstrated by the fact that every variable is above 0.70.

This indicates a high reliability value for the questionnaire set. It is statistically advised that the questionnaire set be used for the research's final data collection considering this finding.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

In this study, convenience sampling technique has been applied to collect the primary data from the agricultural women in Villupuram district. In this way 150 agricultural women are approached to collect the primary data in Villupuram district.

STATISTICAL TOOLS

SEM analysis is used to estimate model by probing the relationship between self-leadership competencies, quality of work life, and life satisfaction. The researcher has employed the SEM analysis for influence of self-leadership competencies on life satisfaction: the role quality of work life.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The table 3 presents the mode summary of mediation effect of quality of work life between self-leadership competencies and self-leadership competencies in Villupuram district. The SEM model presented, along with mode summary to verify the model fitness. The Chi-square statistic is 450.046 with $p < 0.05$.

Table 3: Model fit indication of SEM

S.No.		Model Fit Indicators	Suggested standards (Premapriya, et al. 2016)	Calculated Values
1	Chi-Square Test	Chi-Square	---	450.046
		p	> 0.050	0.0001
2	Goodness Fit	GFI	> 0.90	0.902
		AGFI		0.818
		CFI		0.917
		NFI		0.921
3	Badness Fit	RMR	< 0.080	0.038
		RMSEA		0.049

Source: Primary data

Figure 2: Mediation effect of quality of work life between self-leadership competencies and life satisfaction

Table 4: Regression Weights

DV		IV	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	Beta	P-Value
Quality of Work Life	<---	Self-leadership Competencies	0.142	0.072	7.971	0.521	0.001
Life Satisfaction	<---	Self-leadership Competencies	0.469	0.088	6.941	0.443	0.001
Life Satisfaction	<---	Quality of Work Life	0.142	0.107	3.151	0.190	0.001

Source: primary data

The table illustrates the model fit statistics such as RMSEA, RMR, NFI, CFI, AGFI and GFI. RMR and RMSEA are within than the recommended limit i.e., RMR and RMSEA is less than 0.08 (Indra, Balaji and Velaudham, 2020; Velaudham and Baskar, 2016). AGFI and GFI are within than the recommended limit i.e., AGFI and GFI values are greater than 0.90 (Kantiah Alias Deepak and Velaudham, 2019; Velaudham and Baskar, 2015). All the model

fit statistics imply a moderately model fit (Premapriya, et al. 2016; Victor and Velaudham, 2020) NFI and CFI values are greater than 0.90 (Reena, et al. 2019; Velaudham & Baskar, 2015).

H₁: Self-leadership competencies significantly influence quality of work life among agricultural women.

The hypothesis was tested in SEM model. The finding of the analysis demonstrated that the C.R. value is 7.971; β value is 0.521 and p value is significant. The value of β is 0.521 that self-leadership competencies explains 52.1 percent of the quality of work life. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. Hence, the result demonstrated that the self-leadership competencies significantly influence quality of work life. Windon and Robotham (2021) found that farmers' quality of life was explained by farmers' self-leadership competencies.

Table 5: Mediation effect

DV		Self-leadership Competencies	Quality of Work Life
Quality of Work Life	DE	0.521	0.000
	IDE	0.000	0.000
	TE	0.521	0.000
Life Satisfaction	DE	0.443	0.190
	IDE	0.084	0.000
	TE	0.527	0.190

Source: Primary Data

H₂: Self-leadership competencies significantly influence life satisfaction among agricultural women.

The hypothesis was tested in SEM model. The finding of the analysis demonstrated that the C.R. value is 6.941; β value is 0.443 and p value is significant. The value of β is 0.443 that self-leadership competencies explains 44.3 percent of the life satisfaction. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. Hence, the result demonstrated that the self-leadership competencies significantly

influence life satisfaction. Lee, et al. (2011), physical wellbeing, and quality of life have all been found to be enhanced by family contact and social group participation.

H₃: There is no mediation effect of quality of work life between self-leadership competencies and life satisfaction among agricultural women.

The hypothesis was tested in SEM model. C.R. value is 3.151; the value of β is 0.443. The table also illustrates that direct effect is 0.443, indirect effect is 0.084 and total effect is 0.527. It means that 52.7% mediating effect of quality of work life between self-leadership competencies and life satisfaction. The p-value is significant ($p=0.001$). Hence, the hypothesis (H_{a9}) is accepted. Therefore, there is mediating effect of quality of work life between self-leadership competencies and life satisfaction. Coughenour and Swanson (1988) found that quality of life affects farm life.

FINDINGS AND SUGGESTIONS

- The result demonstrated that the self-leadership competencies significantly influence quality of work life. Windon and Robotham (2021) found that farmers' quality of life was explained by farmers' self-leadership competencies. The following topics should be covered in a leadership program for agricultural women created by extension practitioners: farmers' work-life balance during peak seasons and challenging dialogues with farm women.
- It is found that the self-leadership competencies significantly influence life satisfaction. Lee, et al. (2011), physical wellbeing, and quality of life have all been found to be enhanced by family contact and social group participation. To increase their confidence and improve long-term productivity, farm workers could gain from specialized training programs focused on stress management, work-life balance, workplace safety, and health and wellbeing.

- There is mediating effect of quality of work life between self-leadership competencies and life satisfaction. Coughenour and Swanson (1988) found that quality of life affects farm life. Extension professionals ought to create a course for farmers that covers work-life balance and stress. Work-life imbalance, particularly an excessive amount of time spent working, is known to have a detrimental effect on one's quality of life.

CONCLUSION

The research attempts to identify the quality of work life of agricultural women. The data has been collected from 150 agricultural women in Villupuram district. The research concluded that the self-leadership competencies significantly influence quality of work life. It is found that the self-leadership competencies significantly influence life satisfaction. There is mediating effect of quality of work life between self-leadership competencies and life satisfaction. To increase their confidence and improve long-term productivity, agricultural women could gain from specialized training programs focused on stress management, work-life balance, workplace safety, and health and wellbeing.

REFERENCE

- Bogue, P., & Phelan, J. (2005). Exploring the quality of life of farm families in Ireland: Implications for Extension. *Journal of International Agricultural and Extension Education*, 12(3), 79–90.
- Clark, A. E. (2010). Work, jobs, and well-being across the millennium. In E. Diener, J. F. Helliwell, & D. Kahneman (Eds.), *International differences in well-being*, Oxford University Press, 436–468.
- Coughenour, C. M., & Swanson, L. E. (1988). Rewards, values, and satisfaction with farm work. *Rural Sociology*, 53(4), 442–459.
- Diener, E., Emmons, R.A., Larsen, R.J., & Griffin, S. (1985). Development of the Satisfaction with Life Scale. *Journal of Personality Assessment*, 49(1), 71–75.

- Fullan, M. (2001). *Leading in a culture of change*. Jossey-Bass.
- Gibson, J. L., Ivancevich, J. M., Donnelly, J. H., & Konopaske, R. (2002). *Organizations behavior, structure, processes* (12th ed.). McGraw-Hill.
- Hughes O. E. (2007). Leadership in a managerial context. In: R. Koch & J. Dixon (Eds.), *Public Governance and Leadership*. Deutscher Universitäts-Verlag, 319-340.
- Indra, Balaji and Velaudham (2020). Impact of Social Influence and Safety on Purchase Decision of Green Cosmetic. *International Journal of Future Generation Communication and Networking*, 13 (3), 3036–3042.
- John, M.P. & Joy, M. (2023). Influence of Career Satisfaction on Quality of Work Life of Employees in IT Sector. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 11(3), 1242-1248.
- Josephine Reena, A., Kanthiah Alias Deepak, R., Velaudham, C & Manivannan, M. (2019). Influence of Brand Image on Purchase Intention towards FMCG Products. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, 6 (1), 742-745.
- Judge, T., & Bono, J. (2000). Five-factor model of personality and transformational leadership. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 85(5), 751–765.
- Kantiah Alias Deepak and Velaudham (2019). Marital differences towards consumer buying behaviour. *AJANTA*, 8 (2), 36-45.
- Kashyap, Joseph, and Deshmukh (2016). Employee Well-Being, Life Satisfaction and The Need for Work-Life Balance. *Journal of Ravishankar University (Part-A: Science)*, 22(1), pp.11-23.
- Khoshhal, K. I., & Guraya, S. Y. (2016). Leaders produce leaders and managers produce followers. A systematic review of the desired competencies and standard settings for physicians' leadership. *Saudi Medical Journal*, 37(10), 1061–1067.

- Kleih, S. C., & Kübler, A. (2014). Psychological perspectives: Quality of life and motivation. In Grubler, G., & Hildt, E. (Eds.) *Brain-computer-interfaces in their ethical, social and cultural contexts*. Springer, Dordrecht, 77–84.
- Kong, F. Z., Zhao, L., Zhang, X. B., Tsai, C. H., & Lin, D. D. (2019). Farmers' work-life quality and entrepreneurship will in China. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 787.
- Lee, P. S. N., Leung, L., Lo, V., Xiong, C., & Wu, T. (2011). Internet communication versus face-to-face interaction in quality of life. *Social Indicators Research*, 100, 375–389.
- Mehdi Hosseini, Gholamreza Mehdizadeh Jorjatki (2010). Quality of work life (QWL) and its relationship with performance. *University Of Firouzkouh Branch, Tehran*.
- Molnar, J. J. (1985). Determinants of subjective well-being among farm operators: Characteristics of the individual and the firm. *Rural Sociology*, 50(2), 141–162.
- Nanus, B. (1992). *Visionary leadership: Creating a compelling sense of direction for your organization*. Jossey-Bass.
- Nitsch, U. U. (1987). A persistent culture: Some reflections on Swedish family farming. In B. Galeski & E. Wilkening (Eds.), *Family farming in Europe and America*. Westview Press, 95–115.
- Premapriya, Velaudham and Baskar (2016). Nature of Family Influenced by Consumer Buying Behavior: Multiple Group Analysis Approach. *Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities*, 6 (9), 908-915.
- Ulvenblad, P., & Cederholm Björklund, J. (2018). A leadership development programme for agricultural entrepreneurs in Sweden. *The Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*, 24(4), 327–343.
- Velaudham and Baskar (2015). Multiple Group Structural Equation Model Showing Influence of Age in Consumer Buying Behavior towards Air Conditioner in Chennai City. *Annamalai journal of management*, 89-96.

- Velaudham and Baskar (2016). Number of earning members influence over air conditioner buying behavior: multiple group analysis approach. *Annamalai Business Review*, 10 (2), 59-68.
- Velaudham, C & Baskar, P (2015). Influence of Gender in Consumer Buying Behavior Towards Air Conditioner in Chennai City. *Annamalai Journal of Management*, 3-9.
- Victor Charles and Velaudham (2020). The Impact of Consumer's Perception Towards E-Tailing In Madurai. *High Technology Letters*, 26 (10), 583-593.
- Windon, S. and Robotham, D. (2021). The Relationship Between Farmers' Quality of Life and Their Leadership Competencies. *Advancements in Agricultural Development*, 2 (2), 50-72.
- Windon, S. R., Jepsen, S. D., & Scheer, S. D. (2016). Examining the quality of life of farmers with disabilities: The Ohio AgrAbility Study. *Journal of Agricultural Safety and Health*, 22(1), 3-13.